

AN APHORISM AS A WHOLE STATEMENT: SYSTEMS OF ORGANIZATION INTEGRATING SEMANTIC COMPONENTS

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Abstract:

The relevance of the undertaken research is determined by an integrated approach to the study of an aphorism as an integral text. Of particular importance is the inclusion in the scientific paradigm of the study of those communicative factors, extralinguistic, that determine the production of the text and its interpretation. An aphorism is considered from the standpoint of communicative stylistics as a special type of text, linguoculturally and genre specific. The purpose of the article is to study the basic structural mechanisms of the design of an aphorism as an integral text and the conditioning of such an aphoristic structure on the semantics and pragmatics of an aphorism.

Key words: aphorism, literary text, linguistic and stylistic specificity, structural and semantic features, context, pragmatic effect, value picture of the world.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/wsy eo623>

Modern concepts of communicative stylistics interpret an aphorism as a special text, which is characterized by linguistic-stylistic and genre specificity. Traditionally, aphorisms are understood as judgments that are brevity, characterized by philosophical meaning and completeness in a semantic sense [3]. such judgments retain a connection with the personality of a particular author and have a figurative form [4:3]. aphorisms are also studied from the standpoint of cognitive-pragmatic and linguo-culturological approaches, cf.: "... aphorisms <...> contain a large amount of information about traditions, foundations, the uniqueness of the worldview and mentality of a particular linguistic community" [5:8]. In the scientific paradigm of modern linguistics, it is promising to consider an aphorism as an integral text of a small format, as a statement that has a special semiotic and communication status.

Aphorism as a complex phenomenon is a relevant object of linguistic research, developing in several directions, priority among which are communicative-stylistic, cognitive-pragmatic, linguo-culturological and structural-semantic. communicative stylistics creates the necessary conditions for clarifying specific features of an aphorism, in particular, recognizing its artistic and figurative speech concretization as fundamental. This basic feature of a literary text is determined by a number of extralinguistic factors that distinguish it from figurative concretization in a literary text, and in this regard, it is important that the concept of artistic figurative speech concretization is much broader than the understanding of verbal imagery [1:]. aphorisms are used in a variety of social spheres (science, art, politics, law, religion, everyday life, etc.), in official and informal communicative situations, combining logical and figurative thinking, which is facilitated by a complex of aphorism functions, including aesthetic, communicative, expressive function. In addition, an aphorism is potentially characterized by pragmatic attitudes of reasoning, denunciation and reproach, warning, (self) justification, statement, justification, appeal to authority (including the author himself), motivation, advice, knowledge, aesthetic impact, etc. [6:9]. The study of an aphorism from the standpoint of systemic stylistic analysis and the method

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of linguistic interpretation of a text [7] makes it possible to identify its constitutive features - general significance, expressiveness, information density (conciseness) - and to describe the correlative connections of the logical-semantic and linguistic aspects in an aphorism as a special type of text.

The cognitive-pragmatic direction in the study of aphorisms makes it possible to identify their features that organize aphoristic discourse [8] and the linguistic picture of the world, determined by the mentality of the ethnic group and linguistic personality [9]. the structural-semantic approach focuses on describing the place of aphorisms in the paremic picture of the world, their correlations with proverbs, sayings and other phraseological units [5; 10; 11], and also determines the specifics of an aphorism as a small-format text as a whole [12; 4], including in the aspect of intertextuality [9;5].

As a special type of text, an aphorism is both a speech work, which is characterized by independence, and a microtext (a component of the macro-context) [3], while such characteristics can be applied to the same aphorism [5], which determines its structure and functions. Based on the structural criterion, isolated and introductory aphorisms are distinguished. isolated aphorisms are statements that the author himself qualifies as aphorisms, which allows him to sometimes combine them into separate collections of his own sayings. the very name of the genre - aphorism - is not always represented in the titles of books (for example, "for every day", "The Way of Life" by L. N. Tolstoy); sometimes authors resort to using synonyms of the term (for example, "Maxims and Moral Reasoning" by La Rochefoucauld). nevertheless, there are also cases of including the very name of the genre (for example, "excerpts and aphorisms" by P. Ya. Chaadaev). introductory aphorisms are studied as sayings that are an integral component of an artistic or journalistic, scientific text, which are nevertheless isolated from larger texts on the basis of the implementation of conceptually significant ideas in them (in this case, the marker is lexemes and lexical combinations included in a certain concept sphere) and the possibility of limiting the volume of the introductory aphorism (no more than three sentences).

In our opinion, if the aphorism is not initially isolated, but is presented in the text as its semantic and structural component, as a separate syntactic unit within the text, then it can be studied from the standpoint of linguistics only as an integral text, and its semantic structure in this case acquires a more universal meaning, applicable not only to a specific context from which it is isolated, but also realizing ontological content. in other words, the structural and functional autonomy of an aphorism becomes possible only if its original meaning is transformed when extracted from a specific context in the coordinates of a literary text.

The mechanisms of the structural-semantic organization of an aphorism are determined by certain semantic features of such a complete text: first of all, the aphorism must have a laconic volume, the coordinates of which must contain a certain universal idea that clarifies aspects of human existence, guides his thoughts about universal values, capable of giving answers to ontologically important questions. It is also important to note that the design of an aphoristic statement within an integral text of a larger volume is also influenced by extralinguistic factors that make it possible to translate linguistically and culturally through an aphorism.

Significant meanings elucidation of the mechanisms of the structural organization of aphorisms is necessary, first of all, for their correct isolation from the macrocontext. the semantics of an aphorism must be broader than the context that surrounds it; it must be free from contextual and situational restrictions, for example: "generally speaking, it is not known how much a person needs. probably more than what he needs, and no less than what he wants" [7]. The aphorism given as an example is indeed a statement that has a universal meaning, which is realized through the use of the lexeme person and other grammatical means (pronouns how many, comparative degree of adjectives more, less, etc.).

An aphorism can be included by the author in a wider context in different ways. An aphorism does not always undergo transformations in the text: it may not depend semantically on the context, its representation as an independent text does not entail changes in the structural-semantic and/or lexico-grammatical organization. such aphorisms are autonomous in relation to the surrounding context, for example: "Some of us get paid well. some win on loans. Some people even know where they get their money from. but we have little idea what wealth is" [8]. We emphasize here that the autonomy of the highlighted aphoristic statement can be recognized through the use of the pronouns we and some, which expands the applicability of the verbalized situation to the widest addressee.

One of the important semantic features that determine the structure of an aphorism as an integral text of a special type is its general validity. General validity is understood as a certain value of information recorded by an aphorism for a wide addressee. the cognitive basis of general significance is formed by the relevance of the subject of speech and the philosophical depth of the statement, provided, in turn, by ontological meanings. in the structure of an aphorism, universal validity appears as an explication of didacticism. for example, M. Zoshchenko: "science is imperfect. truth is the daughter of time" [9]. universal significance receives consistent implementation here, first of all, because it refers the addressee to his background knowledge and experience: indeed, a person cannot comprehend the truth in an instant, this requires work and time. In our opinion, this aphorism also has special pragmatics due to the author's effective implementation of laconic statements and their strict logical sequence: science is a "tool for comprehending truth" - truth.

In a specific literary text in which the introductory aphorism is differentiated, general significance can have different shades: these are the edifying, pragmatic or contemplative-informative orientation of general significance. however, in all cases of realization of general significance, the priority remains the generality of the judgment, supported by the expressiveness of their speech design, for example: "war will become absurd, I think, when technology reaches an absolute hit" [9]. in the above aphorism, universal significance is achieved by appealing to the universal values of humanity and anti-war pathos, while the semantics of the aphorism is clarified by highlighting those pragmatic features that characterize modern changing world: the author proves that war will then cease to be a popular way of resolving contradictions when the technical means of waging it become impeccable in terms of the effectiveness of achieving results.

Paradoxically, an aphorism retains its general validity even in the case of zero realization of generality, which can be observed in aphorisms of a specific historical or epigrammatic nature, for example: "Actually, we don't have any rich people. but we have wealthy people" [8]. We especially emphasize here that the opposition, which is the basis of the structural-semantic organization of the aphorism, has a specific historical origin, since M. Zoshchenko creates his literary texts in the first years of Soviet power, which means that the denial of wealth is included in the official ideology. nevertheless, it is clear that it is precisely the discrepancy with ideological guidelines that forms the basis of satire in Zoshchenko's texts, therefore the use of synonyms rich and prosperous acquires new clarifying stylistic and semantic shades.

General significance can also be realized in those aphorisms that, at first glance, are statements characterized by an ironic or humorous orientation. in such aphorisms, evaluativeness comes to the fore, manifesting the components of the author's value picture of the world, for example: "The patient is worthless now. that is, everyone strives to get treatment for nothing using an insurance card" [7]. the addressee is initially convinced that here the author proves the importance of the main goal of medicine - providing assistance to the patient, ultimately aimed at healing, and not at obtaining profit. The pragmatic effect

arises due to the proof of this truth “from the opposite”, which, moreover, is enhanced by means of the colloquial style (worthless, insurance card, free treatment).

Thanks to originality, the contradictions between the meaning of an aphorism and the reader’s extra-linguistic experience or language norms can be actualized, for example: “the mind is a dark matter” [7]. Traditionally, in Russian linguistic culture, the mind is understood as that which leads to the light of knowledge, therefore the paradoxical nature of the semantics of an aphorism allows the author to achieve the necessary pragmatic effect: the statement is easily remembered. In addition, this aphorism also has a deep philosophical meaning - indeed, the mechanisms of human cognitive activity are difficult to comprehend, since the observer necessarily turns out to be at the same time a participant in the experiment (it is impossible to observe the activity of consciousness in isolation, without involving the cognitive mechanisms of one’s own mind).

Alogism, which forms the foundation for the realization of the originality of an aphorism, consists of an unexpected combination of phenomena and objects that are not correlated in everyday life. Thanks to illogicality, the author gets the opportunity to express in a laconic form the entire semantics of artistic images, often in this way defining his own artistic principles and demonstrating the value picture of the world in an artistic text, for example: “and stupidity is not a headache that goes away with powder” [7]. in the above aphorism, the pragmatic effect is fixed by comparing the incomparable (stupidity is a headache), revealing a significant component of the value the author's world pictures.

An important feature of an aphorism, which determines its structural and semantic organization, is also its information density (conciseness), for example: “It is a great misfortune not to love anyone” [9].

Analysis of the research material allows us to talk about the importance of intertextuality in the structural and semantic organization of aphorisms. Thus, M. Zoshchenko refers to well-known texts, indicating their author, for example: “various sublime thoughts pass through. Various humane phrases are crowded in my head. different poems come to mind. something like this comes to mind from Pushkin: “Daddy, daddy, our nets brought in a dead man...” [6]. in the given aphoristic statement the name of the author of the poetic lines is verbalized, and the poetic fragment itself from the poem by A.S. Pushkin “The Drowned Man” (1828) is intended to evoke broad linguistic and cultural associations in the reader. The comedy of the aphorism lies here in its illogicality, because there is a semantic contrast between the lexical combinations of sublime thoughts, humane phrases and lines included in this aphoristic context. Also, a representative example of the intertextuality of the aphorism: “Rough age. Rough manners. there is no romanticism” [7]. in our opinion, the implicit reference to the final phrase of Pushkin’s “miserly knight” (1830) “terrible age, terrible hearts!”, pronounced by the Duke as a moralistic conclusion, receives here not only a lexical, but also a semantic transformation, and its sublime pathos is reduced by the vernacular formalizing the thought “there is no romanticism” and replacing the adjective terrible with rude. We find an even more complex case of the implementation of intertextuality in the following aphorism by M. Zoshchenko: “reason conquers suffering. but the “sufferers” do not want to give up their positions.

Conclusion. This article makes an attempt to systematize the mechanisms of the structural and semantic organization of an aphorism as an integral text and, on this basis, to establish criteria for isolating an aphoristic statement from a larger literary text. elucidating the factors that determine the semantics and pragmatics of an aphorism as a special type of text seems relevant for modern linguistics due to the blurring of boundaries and the lack of a clear methodology for a relatively new field of research - aphorism. aphorisms act as individual statements characterized by general significance, expressiveness, and laconic volume. one of the important factors that can influence the structure and semantics of an aphorism is intertextuality. in addition, alogism, which often forms the basis of the structure

of an aphorism, is capable of imparting additional expressiveness to an aphoristic statement and revealing ontologically significant meanings thanks to a unique form of representation of an idea.

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